

ANAPHORA AND ITS IMPORTANCE

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Annotation: Anaphora is a rhetorical image widely used among poets and lyric writers. It consists of the constant repetition of a word or phrase, generally used at the beginning of a verse or sentence.

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Anaphora should not be confused with epiphora. Although its use is very similar, if a repeated word or phrase is at the end of a sentence, it is called an epiphora. Anaphora and epiphora are given in the same subject and they can be repeated in turn during speech. The anaphora in rhetoric can consist of several words; yes, the unit selected accordingly is required to be repeated throughout the speech.

Anaphora (repetition) - a line in a poem or verse, the exact repetition of a word or phrase at the beginning of a sentence at the beginning of other verses. Example:

Endi odam quldek sotilmas,
Endi odam o'tga otilmas,
Endi unga qafas bo'lmas jon
Endi dunyo bo'lmaydi zindon

Hamid Olimjon's Patience in "Zaynab and Omon"

The word anaphora is of Latin origin "anaphora" and is derived from the Greek, it is formed with the prefix "ana" What does this mean "or against the" Y "forum" from the verb "perein" This means "wear In the sense of rhetoric, it is a literary person who repeats a word or group of words at the beginning of a verse or phrase.

Miguel Hernandez's poem "El Silbo del Dale" is a living example of an anaphora: 'guncha ur. Give water until it turns to stone The word Anaphora is of Latin origin "anaphora" and is derived from the Greek, it is formed with the prefix "Ana" What does this mean "or" Y "forum" from the verb "perein" This Miguel Hernandez's poem "El Silbo del Dale" is a living example of an anaphora: "A knife, a mill, a wheat snow." shoot until it rains. Give him water until he turns to stone. "In grammar, what this anaphora means is from a linguistic context, that is, the existence of a set of elements that reflect the above-mentioned question. In this sense, suffixes, rhymes, and verbs, which can be called anaphora, are used because it avoids repeating words that have been said before, such as: "Hector presented his work and the family applauded him." Anaphora is only lexical. , but can also be audible. For example, "Good morning!" in the poem. Sergei Yesenin, two series begin with the same sound combinations: Anaphoras are called syntactic if they consist of the same or similar constructions. This stylistic figure was portrayed by Konstantin Balmont in his "Say it for a moment: stop!" used in poetry.

" Balki butun tabiat gullar mozaikasidir?

Balki barcha Tabiat ovozlardagi farqdir?

Ehtimol, barcha Tabiat faqat raqamlar va xususiyatlardir?

Balki butun tabiat go'zallikka intilishdir?

How to use the word "Anafora" in a sentence

The Mozarabic liturgy, unlike other liturgical families, has two or three anaphors (Eucharistic prayers) and uses at least one a week, which is more than two hundred. He began to use some of the obvious things that were in the minds of the interlocutors to express them in anaphora. Anaphora rhythm. The repetition of a certain word or phrase at the beginning of a verse creates an anaphora rhythm.

Bir qarasam, do'stu yordan ko'nglim to'qday,
Bir qarasam, atrofimda hech kim yo'qday.
Bir qarasam, suyanchiqday bolalarim,
Bir qarasam, ular siniq lolalarim
Bir qarasam, bu dunyoda baxtim borday,
Bir qarasam, butun olam menga torday.
Bir qarasam, murodinga yetgandayman,
Bir qarasam, ko'zim ochiq ketgandayman.
Bir qarasam, shon-shuhratga yo'g'rilganman,
Bir qarasam, endigina tug'ilganman

In the example of Abdulla Aripov's poem "Bir karasam ..." we conclude that the rhythm of "Bir karasam" is repeated several times, but not all of them are expressed in the same way. Each has a different pronunciation. Only when it is read expressively can we reveal the content of the poem, its essence. We know that expressive reading has always been accompanied by a voice. Reading aloud, not just the verses in a poem, but the whole work or a short text, makes it easier for students to develop their understanding. Anaphora is a stylistic figure of speech, a cycle of poetic speech consisting of the repetition of initial consonants, parts of speech, phrases, and syntactic constructions.

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